

REFLECTIONS OF THE COMPETITIVE ACTIVITY SYSTEM OF YOUNG HANDBALL PLAYERS AND ITS SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS

Наргиза Шермухамедова

Ўзбекистон Миллий университети,
Таэквандо ва спорт фаолияти кафедраси ўқитувчиси.

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Abstract. *This article analyses some issues related to the training of handball players of the training group of the specialized sports school for children and teenagers. Particularly, the educational normative documents belonging to the group, the planning of loadings by its types of preparation, during the annual cycle, the program materials, their structure and content were examined.*

Keywords: *young handball players, curriculum, planning, distribution of training hours, technical and tactical actions, the volume of technical and tactical actions, the effectiveness of technical and tactical actions.*

СТРУКТУРА СОРЕВНОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ЮНЫХ ГАНБОЛИСТОВ И ЕЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ

Аннотация. *В статье исследуются вопросы касающейся подготовки юных гандболистов учебно-тренировочных групп, специализированных детских и юношеских спортивных школ. В частности, исследована учебно-нормативная документация, планирование учебных нагрузок по видам подготовок на разных этапах годовичного цикла, их содержание и структура, а также структура соревновательной деятельности юных гандболистов.*

Ключевые слова: *юные гандболисты, учебная программа, планирование, распределение учебных часов, технико-тактические действия, объём технико-тактических действий, эффективность технико-тактических действий.*

In our country, handball is one of the most important sports in the system of physical education and sports. Because playing handball has a positive effect on the player's organism in many ways and closely contributes to physical development and increase of functional capabilities.

As for the issues of professional training of handball players in Uzbekistan, it should be noted that issues of handball development have not lost their relevance today [1]. Because the few positive results achieved by our handball players in international competitions are the basis for such a conclusion.

Today, one of the main factors in increasing the international reputation of handball and achieving high results is the training of reserve athletes. Among the main aspects of training that deserve attention are the issues of correctly and rationally planning the training loads at the stages of the multi-year training process, ensuring their compatibility with the age, gender and level of training of the participants [4].

Another aspect is the management of preparation through rational planning of training loads based on the characteristics of the competition and the results (indicators) recorded in it, experts in the field emphasize. Among the factors that ensure the effectiveness of the competition, it is recognized by experts that the tools and methods used in the training are suitable for the

periods and stages of the training, and the direction of the loads depends on the suitability of the tasks of the training [5,6].

Modern handball is characterized by high demands on athletes' training. The intense nature of competition conditions, the fact that technical and tactical actions performed by athletes are required to be carried out quickly, in a short period of time, and in conditions of high activity of resistance from the opponent's players, set the highest requirements for competition preparation [2,7]. In this regard, experts in the field emphasize that first of all, knowing the structure of the existing competition, having a clear idea about its specific features, is considered as a factor that allows for more effective management of future preparation processes.

The purpose of the study. Studying the structure of the competition activity of the training group handball players and determining their characteristics.

Methods of research work: analysis of scientific and methodical literature related to the topic, methods of pedagogical observation and recording of the process of competition activity, methods of mathematical and statistical analysis of the collected results.

Results of research work.

The problems of training and competition load control have been widely researched by mature specialists such as V.M. Zatsiorsky, Yu.V. Verkoshansky, L.P. Matveev, M.A. Godik. Our local scientists T. E. Nabiev, J. A. Akramov conducted relevant research in these areas. The issues of training young athletes were studied by V. Ignateva, A. Gamayun, V. P. Filin, N. A. Fomin, N. J. Bulgakova, L. P. Makarenko and others. At the same time, it is worth saying that the analysis of special sources has shown that the issues of training of young handball players in Uzbekistan have not been paid enough attention to this point, and that research aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the training process has not been carried out in this regard.

According to the results of a number of relevant research studies, the indicators reflecting the competition activity of highly qualified and young handball players are sharply different from each other. It is known that young handball players (13 years old) perform more mobility activities compared to adults. It has been determined that during the 40 minutes of the competition, young people perform the same amount of attacking movements as they do during the 60 minutes of competition for adults. A third of the attacks in young people correspond to the proportion of very fast attacks. But the efficiency indicators of movements will have lower manifestations than those of skilled athletes. For this reason, experts emphasize that it is necessary to pay attention to this aspect when working with young people.

A number of research works carried out by V. Ignateva made it possible for young handball players to have a detailed information base about the structure of competition activities. It is known from the studies that during the execution of offensive actions in girls, the actions of hitting the goal in the base position are caught in 33-34% of the total shots, and by the age of 15-16, this figure is observed to decrease to 25%, that is, as the age of the athlete grows, his complex actions the ratio of execution increases and vice versa the ratio of simple actions decreases. In the case of boys, the actions of hitting the goal in the base position are relatively stable in competitive conditions (around 30-35%), by the age of 15, the proportion of such shots is 24% of the total shots.

Attempts to shoot at the goal in a jumping position are made in 43-60% of cases compared to total attempts. In girls, this indicator was 50-65%. Another type of kicking movement is the most complicated one, which is a jump shot. In girls, these actions account for 4-15% of total strokes, and in boys, this figure is 10-23%. At the age of 13-14, the ratio of such blows in boys is found to increase to 25%. The specialist suggests that this period should be evaluated as a sensitive period in the formation of complex manifestations of shock [5,6].

Competition studies have provided information on turnovers. In particular, the cases of 16-year-old handball players losing the ball in different situations during the competition were as follows:

- losing the ball by pressing the line – 20%;
- exclusion from the game - 16%;
- due to receiving a red card - 6%;
- due to errors in carrying the ball – 6%;
- probe – 12%;
- error in catching the ball -10%;
- error in passing the ball - 20%;
- carrying the ball in two hands - 6%;
- in other cases – 4%.

According to the results of personal pedagogical observation and analysis, there was not enough balance between the training loads of the young handball players of the 1st training group of the specialized sports school for children and teenagers and the structures of competition activities. Experts admit that the observation of such a situation is negative. Planned loadings for the development of technical and tactical movements of athletes in complex game situations do not fully reflect the characteristics of the competition, that is, the ratios of movement recorded by the athletes during the competition are manifested in other ratios during training. In most cases, it is being developed in insufficient proportions, that is, time is allocated [3]. This situation, in turn, prevents the training from becoming more effective. In the loading planning program, 40% of the time was devoted to improving the passing movements in the active phases of the attack and only 5% of the time was organized in the closing phases of the attacks. However, it was found out from the pedagogical observation of handball players of this age during the competition activity that the majority of them used ball passing movements in the final phases of attacks. This situation is the basis for our conclusion that the distribution of hours planned for loading during training was not carried out in a rational way.

Team	Various technical and tactical actions of passing the ball						In total meeting EIT
	In the passive phase of the attack		In the active phase of the attack		In the final phase of the attack		
Specialized sports school for children and teenagers	The number of	Ratio %	The number of	Ratio %	The number of	Ratio %	

	moveme nt		moveme nt		moveme nt		
<i>EIT volume</i>	93 ± 9	49	74 ± 7	39	22 ± 4	12	190 ± 14
<i>EIT TA %</i>	75.5		59.4		38.2		57.3

Note: EIT TA % - efficiency indicator of technical and tactical actions %

Conclusions. Issues of organizing the training of young handball players in our country remain relevant. In this case, one of the main aspects is to ensure that the issues of planning the training load are in accordance with the requirements of the time.

The analysis of the results of personal research showed that a large number of mistakes were made in the main technical and tactical actions performed by young handball players during the competition. In complex game situations, in particular, in the active and final phases of the attack, the effectiveness indicators of the technical-tactical actions of passing the ball were at a low level.

It is necessary to improve the effectiveness of technical and tactical actions in the active or final phases of offensive actions. For this, rational planning of training loads should be understood as the main issue. In order to ensure the high efficiency of the actions performed in game situations where a strong opponent opposes, it is necessary to organize the training processes of athletes in such a way (planning of training loads), the tools and methods used in the process should serve for the development of these actions and help to increase the level of special training of athletes.

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